

THE IMPACT OF VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE ON CAREER CHOICE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL IN UMUAHIA NORTH LGA, ABIA STATE

ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of vocational guidance on career choice of secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Specifically, this study ascertained the extent to which vocational guidance has been able to impact on career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State; the extent to which vocational guidance can practically reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers; the factors influencing career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State; and the factors that affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State. The study was guided by a descriptive survey design because it gives detailed information about issues, problems, events and describes events as they are. Both primary data were used. The population of this study consists of ten (10) secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA; which consists of junior basic III and upper basic III Students about to write their certificate examination. A total number of two hundred (200) students was selected for this study. The researcher used questionnaire for data collection. The data gathered for the study was analyzed using descriptive analysis using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The results of the study reveal that increased awareness of the students, enhanced decision-making skills, educational alignment to the students, by providing clear information about career options and required qualifications to the students, effective vocational guidance programs often provide access to additional resources such as career fairs, internships, and mentorships, providing personalized support to the students, the impact of vocational guidance may be limited by factors such as inadequate resources, lack of trained counselors, or limited, and exposure to diverse career options are the extent to which vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. The study also finds that by providing accurate information about different career paths, vocational guidance helps students identify and develop skills that are in demand in the job market, it students understand the educational and training requirements for various careers, its create job market awareness to the students, its create soft skills development to the students, career counselling can connect students with professionals and potential employers, providing networking opportunities that can lead to job placements, to create entrepreneurial guidance to the students, and to reduced job search time are how vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. All the items raised on the educational factors that shape the career aspirations of motor vehicle mechanics works student were accepted by the respondents, as their mean responses exceeded the critical mean 2.5. Additionally, the study observes that availability of trained personnel, resource allocation to the students, curriculum integration in secondary schools, providing support from school administration, community and parental involvement, peer influence, student engagement to the course, access to information, cultural and social factors, infrastructure and facilities, and monitoring and evaluation are the factors that influence or affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary school in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State. The study on the impact of vocational guidance on career choice among secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia, has demonstrated that vocational guidance plays a crucial role in shaping the career aspirations of students. It was found that students who received adequate vocational guidance were better able to make informed decisions about their future careers. It is recommended that schools in Umuahia North LGA should strengthen and expand their vocational guidance programs, and career guidance should be integrated into the secondary school curriculum, ensuring that students have access to structured programs that will help them make informed decisions about their career paths.

Background of the Study

A vocation is an occupation to which a person is especially drawn or for which they are suited, trained or qualified. Vocational education is education that prepares people to work as technicians or to take up employment in a skilled craft or trade as a tradesperson or artisan. Vocational Education can also be seen as that type of

education given to an individual to prepare him/her to be gainfully employed or self-employed with requisite skill (Payton, 2016).

People obtain given information about a new occupation through Vocational guidance. Vocational guidance is the assistance given to an individual to choose a vocation, prepare for it, enter upon and

progress in it. Vocational guidance helps in giving of information, experience and advice in regard to choosing an occupation, preparing for it, entering upon it and progress in it. There are so many vocations as there are so many individuals; and certainly all individuals are not suitable for all the vocations (Osipow *et al.*, 2019). Every vocation needs certain background, preparation and aptitude and only those having them can succeed. The business of the vocational guidance worker is to find out what positions and jobs are available and what their requirements are and to find out whether the person under observation fulfils those conditions (Maxwell and Okwulehie, 2015).

Literally, guidance is as old as mankind. All through the ages, humans have for one reason or the other sought guidance. Vocational guidance was developed by Frank Parsons in the year 1908, a time he was faced with the challenge of giving a name to what he thinks the school should provide as a service to school leavers about to go into the world of work (Dick, 2017). According to Parsons in his book, choosing a vocation, the term vocational guidance was referred to as the process of assisting people choose a vocation, prepare for it and attain efficiency and success. Vocational guidance can be regarded as choosing an occupation, preparing for it and entering into it and progressing in it (Daniel, 2013). In the Nigerian case vocational guidance started formally in 1959 at St. Theresa's College Oke-Ado in Ibadan by some reverend sisters out of sympathy for the products of their school. They felt that these secondary school leavers would have problems in seeking for admission for further studies, looking for employment and adjusting to the hard conditions of the society after leaving school (Hahs-Vaughn, 2016). They then invited some resource persons on various fields on the world of work and personal adjustment in the society. In Nigeria, students lack adequate occupational information before they enter into occupations. In some cases, the

students concern themselves with reading up courses in the schools without due regard to the marketability and employability of the graduates in the field (Hooley, 2012).

Career choice is not one that is made abruptly. It is a continuous process. Career is a series of jobs that a person has in a particular area of work, usually involving more responsibilities as time passes. Career development and choice should be initiated as early as the nursery school years through the primary, secondary and to the tertiary school level (Ipaya, 2015). One's career choice is mostly influenced by parents, friends, relatives, teachers, printed information, etc.

It seems making appropriate career choice has become an uphill task among secondary school students in Umuahia North; consequently, vocational guidance as an area of guidance and counselling has been introduced in secondary schools to help tackle this problem. Vocational guidance serves as a pivotal tool in molding, rebuilding and assuaging the risk of making wrong career choice by secondary school students (Kehinde, 2014). Career selection is one of many important choices students will make in determining future plans; this decision will impact them throughout their lives. The essence of who the student is will revolve around what the student wants to do with their life-long work. Indeed, vocational and career related issues are salient across different cultures and nationalities Leung (2014). In an age of economic globalization, all individuals are affected by an array of work related concerns; some of these concerns are unique to certain cultures, but others are not too many cultural groups.

Even with limited subject options offered by many Nigerian secondary schools; the students seem to have difficulty choosing subjects to study for the West African School Certificate Examination because their teachers cannot help them secure relevant information on career options (Udoh, 2017). Many students do not know

the relationship between the subjects they are being taught in school and their dream careers. It is therefore important to stress on the need for vocational guidance in secondary schools.

Statement of the Problem

It is a common knowledge that education is the bedrock upon which quality career is founded. Yet, troublesome to know that, a good number of young school leavers often take occupational careers other than their educational field of study. Nevertheless, a few number stick to their field of study in their career pursuit, especially for those who undergo professional courses such as Law, Medicine, and Geology etc. It therefore suggests that other fields of study other than the professional fields, are not a good career preparatory step or that their curriculum of studies has not inculcated the right measures for good transition of students into occupational careers (Williams, 2016).

Again, it is interesting to know that most young school leavers undergoing professional studies are mostly from well to do homes, who can afford private secondary schools with high tuition fees, while majority of students undergoing the general field of studies are students from poor and average home backgrounds hence, mainly attending government secondary schools due to the considerable low tuition fee.

The high rate of unemployment and underemployment among school leavers and graduates in Nigeria is a serious issue for concern. It is contended that one of the contributing factors of unemployment cum under employment among school leavers in the country could be inadequate or lack of vocational guidance to students while in and out of school. In other words they are not given sufficient and relevant vocational or occupational information that will enable them graduate from school to a suitable occupation. It is through a graduate's occupation that he/she is expected to serve the country, contribute and at the same time benefit from economic growth and national

development. In a case where is not properly guided on career decision making by a professional guidance counsellor; it would not be possible for such individual to contribute to economic and national development after graduation (Dick, 2018). On another view point, guidance and counselling programmes in secondary schools and tertiary has not been given the proper attention it deserves; and until the proper attention is given to this form of education programme, majority of secondary school students will continue to have difficulty in career decision making. Many secondary school students lack ideas on which course to study in the higher education institution after leaving secondary school. Also the list of vocations appears inexhaustible, likewise the variety of persons with varied attributes; and certainly not all persons are suitable for all vocations because every vocation needs certain background, preparation and aptitude; therefore, only those that have the requirements succeed. More so, the advent of civilization, industrialization and technological development opened a wide variety of new occupations; the problem of selecting occupation by students becomes complex and difficult.

Vocational guidance plays a crucial role in shaping the career choices of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State, by providing them with informed insights into various career paths. Many students may not be fully aware of the range of job opportunities available or the qualifications needed for specific careers. Effective vocational guidance helps bridge this knowledge gap by offering career counseling, exposing students to different fields through workshops or internships, and helping them align their interests and strengths with viable career options. Hence, the present study seeks to determine the impact of vocational guidance on career choice of secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of vocational guidance on career choice of secondary school in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine the extent to which vocational guidance has been able to impact on career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.
- ii. Determine the extent to which vocational guidance can practically reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers.
- iii. Determine the factors influencing career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.
- iv. Determine the factors that affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- i. To what extent has vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State?
- ii. How does vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers?
- iii. What factors influence the career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State?
- iv. What are the factors that influence or affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary school in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State?

Significance of the Study

Result of this study will be beneficial to students, technicians, government, the management of Technical Colleges of Education and the society at large. Graduate

students would benefit from this work because the findings would help graduates of industrial technology education to be self-dependence. This would be possible because the result of the study would guide them on how to be self-employed. The graduate students will benefit from this work if the work is published and kept in the reference library.

The outcome of the study would offer future researchers information on the opportunity factors that affect vocational guidance and career choice of motor vehicle mechanic skills among students. The research scholars would benefit from this work if the work is published and kept in the reference library.

The Management of Technical Colleges of Education would benefit from this work because the result of the study would help the management of technical colleges of education to evaluate vocational guidance and career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. The study would bring more information on the environmental factors that affect vocational guidance and career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. This would be possible if the work is published in journals.

Scope of the Study

This study is delimited to the impact of vocational guidance on career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. The content scope of the study was limited to determining the extent to which vocational guidance has been able to impact on career choice, the extent to which vocational guidance can practically reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers, the factors influencing career decision making, and the factors that affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter covered the conceptual frameworks, theoretical framework and

empirical studies. The conceptual frameworks covered the following: concept of vocation, vocational guidance, career management, career choice, environmental factors among. The theoretical framework covered the trait and factor theory, Tiedeman and O'hara Ego identity theory and Acquired Needs theory. The empirical review of the study covered the related empirical studies.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Impact

2.1.2 Vocation

2.1.3 Vocational Guidance

2.1.4 Career Management

2.1.5 Career choice

2.1.6 Environmental factors

2.1.7 Secondary Schools in Umuahia North

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1.1 Impact

Impact refers to the measurable influence or effect that vocational guidance programs have on the students' career decision-making processes. This impact can be evaluated in terms of how effectively these programs help students identify their strengths, interests, and career options, as well as how they prepare them to make informed decisions about their future educational and career paths. Vocational guidance plays a critical role in increasing students' awareness of various career options. The impact here refers to how well these programs expose students to a wide range of professions, including those they might not have considered, and help them understand what different careers entail. For instance, through workshops, counseling sessions, and career fairs, students gain insights into the requirements and expectations of various fields, which can significantly broaden their horizons (Gysbers, 2013).

Another significant impact of vocational guidance is on the students' decision-making abilities. Effective vocational guidance equips students with the skills to evaluate their own interests, abilities, and values against the demands and rewards of

different careers. This aspect of impact involves the extent to which vocational guidance helps students develop critical thinking and self-assessment skills necessary for making informed career choices (Brown & Lent, 2016).

Vocation

A vocation is an occupation to which a person is especially drawn or for which are suited, trained or qualified. People can be given information about a new occupation through student orientation. Though now often used in non-religious contexts, the meanings of the term originated in Christianity (Mutekwe, 2011). A vocation can refer to a particular occupation that leverages a person's skills toward a wider purpose. This type of vocation isn't limited to a single job. There are many ways to answer a calling. The concept of vocation as a calling or life purpose has its roots in early religious figures individuals who are called of a divine power to perform special work on earth. Many times, the call of these first prophets is described in mystical terms.

Vocational Guidance

Vocational guidance, according to Parsons (1909) is the processes of helping an individual match his personal attributes and his background with suitable jobs and employment opportunities. Super and Crites (1962) expanded the above definition by saying that vocational guidance is the process of helping the individual to ascertain, accept, understand and apply the relevant facts about occupational world.

Super (1957) defines the enterprise of vocational guidance as the process of helping a person to develop and accept an integrated picture of himself, and his role in the world of work, to test this concept against reality and to convert it into reality with satisfaction to himself and benefit to society. A definition of this kind, unlike that of Parsons' conceives vocational guidance as a task that should begin with a teaching function explicitly designed to locate for the individual the type of person he is; with a view to ushering in for the client, that required level of self-knowledge he needs

to be able to come to a decision about what to do in life. In line with the above explanation, Newton (2015) noted that through vocational guidance individuals are given universal attention in understanding the meaning of work in human life; including survival trends in the career world; vocations that are available; and those vital factors and forces one has to consider or way, to make an informed career choice.

Vocational guidance and counselling experts believes that each individual has certain abilities, interests, and personality traits band other characteristics. It is the confidence of these professionals that of these characteristics are known together with their latent values and where on the job-market these values can be put into appropriate uses, the individual is more likely to become a happier person, a more effective worker and a more useful citizen. According to Ipay (2015) knowledge of oneself and knowledge of the opportunities existing in one's environment and in particular, knowledge of what one can do that employers would be willing to pay for can help an individual make a good vocational adjustment. Also, self-knowledge and occupational knowledge are very important means of ensuring accurate and adequate occupational choice. There are innovative processes necessary to bring about these self and social understating which are so vital for good vocational guidance programme. These innovative processes are those of vocational guidance.

Career Management

Career management is defined by Onayase (2019) as the planning and shaping of the progression or movement of individuals within an organization by aligning employee preferences, talent and potential with organizational resourcing needs both now and in the future.

Kehinde (2014) also defined Career management as the process by which individuals collect information about values, interests, skills, strengths and weaknesses, identify a career goal, and

engage in career strategies that increase the probability that career goals will be achieved. The failure to motivate employees to plan their careers can result in a shortage of employees to fill open positions, it can also lower employee commitment and inappropriate use of monies allocated for training and development programs (Abuda, 2015).

Using career management approach, employers can coach the employee in his individual career planning, and by realizing the plans of employees, he can also plan the allocation of human resources. Thus, the career development is perceived like joint effort between the individual employee nad the organization. Career management describes the lifelong process of managing life, learning and work. It involves individuals planning and making decisions about education, training and career choices as well as developing the right skills and knowledge to do this (Robert, 2012).

Kehinde (2014) and Robert (2012) argued that career management involves aligning individual subjective and more objective career aspects of an organization to find a match between individuals and organizational needs, personal characteristics and career roles. They view career development as a natural role, based on the needs and circumstances of both individuals and organizations. Development involves preparing employees for higher responsibilities in future. Development can be seen as the use of human resources to quantitatively change man's physical and biological environments to his benefits or ever seen as involving the introduction of new ideas into the social structure and causing alterations on the patterns of the organization and social structure (Leung, 2014).

To develop staff simply refers to making them grow with the organization so that they can be fitted for available higher position within their capacity. Development deals with improving human relations and interpersonal skills. Career development covers an employee's working life. It starts

with staff orientation, on-job training, experience, short courses, professional courses, postgraduate degrees or diplomas. According to the 2013 National Strategy for the development of social service workforce in Scotland, employee development is the foundation on which the confidence and competence of individual staff is built (Whiston, 2018).

Employees are major assets of any organization like banks and they play an active role towards organizational success that cannot be underestimated. Equipping these unique assets through effective training becomes imperative in order to maximize the job performance. Career management is often used to close the gap between current performance and expected future performance. Many employees in different organizations have trained but they have remained stagnant with little evidence of career advancement (Mutekwe *et al.*, 2011).

Biermen (2014) defines career development in two areas: Career development is a change of values, attitudes, and motivations that occur in a person due to the addition, and improvement will become more mature age. This understanding shows that the focus of career development is the increase in mental abilities that occurs as you age. Therefore, the change is perceived as a mental process that is in a person, it is called also the subjective sense. Secondly, career development is the work done by the ongoing formal and focused on improving and adding the ability of a worker. Career development includes improvements made to achieve personal and career goals plan (Khallad, 2019). Companies must pay attention to the needs of the employee's career in order to retain productive employees.

Career development is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future. Career Development services are programs and services that are

intended to help individuals to explore and sort out questions related to employability, direction, skills development, personal development, progression, and making a difference. Such services are provided in many different settings (Williams, 2016).

Career development is about navigating your journey through learning and work. Career management is the combination of structured planning and the active management choice of one's own professional career. Career management was first defined in a social work doctoral thesis by Mary Valentich as the implementation of a career strategy through application of career tactics in relation to chosen career orientation (Daniels, 2013).

Career management is the process which plans and shapes the profession of individuals within an organization in accordance with organizational needs and objectives. According to Onayase (2019), a typical career management programme as part of the larger human resources system involves efforts aimed at helping employees to assess their own career, strengths and weakness; set priorities and specific career goals, provides information on various career path and alternatives within the organization and other employees yearly reviews of their progress towards these goals by managers who have received training in conducting such assessment. Career management assesses employees to improve their performance by involving employee in setting their own goals and recognizing their strengths and weakness (Sears, 2015). It assists employees with the organization with the identification and facilitation of training needs and opportunities. This is mainly achieved by building a process of feedback and discussion into the performance management system of institutions. Career management clarifies available career options. Employees are informed of career options available with the organization. It assists employee with the identification of skills and other qualities required for current and future jobs most career

management performance seek to focus employees career plans upon the organization thereby enhancing their commitment to the organization. In doing this, careers path are developed that indicates mobility in different directions in the organization for the employees (Udoh, 2017).

Career choice

Career choice is a decision making process. It is a development process which spans one's life. It transcends just choosing a job for an immediate satisfaction and entails a serious consideration of a job and its implication for later satisfaction and personal adjustments (Tella, 2017).

Career selection is one of the main important choices a student will have to take in his life. This choice of decision will have impact on them throughout their lives. Career plays a very fundamental and significant role in the life of the individual because it determines the pattern of his or her income, affects the individual's personality and concept of life. Therefore, career is a life time pursuit for success. It is the sequence of major positions occupied by a person throughout his life time. The term career is broadly defined as all like roles people play including students, parents, employees, retirees and employers, in securing a livelihood. Authur (2016) thus indicates that career is the totality of experience through which one learns about and prepares to engage in work as part of his way of living. In a nutshell, career is the totality of work one does in his life time to earn a living. It's therefore a positive thing for one to think as far as possible in achieving this fit. Hence making a career choice is essential for everyone.

Career choice is something very hard to make especially as one's livelihood depends on it. Career choice has become a complex task among students in the face of ever changing technology and the information sector. Career refers to job or series of job that you do during your working life (Rojewski, 2016). Thus choosing a career simply means choosing a

life job. Career choice is affected by multiple factors include personality, interest, self-concept, identity, globalization, socialization, role model, social support and available resources such as information and finance. Onayase and Onayase, (2019) also carried out an investigation into other factors that could affect career choice, thus, identified religion, peer group and some environmental factors. However, all careers have their subject requirements, personality characteristics and personal abilities. All these are supposed to be fully assessed before an individual can be verified to be qualified into a specific career (Onayase and Onayase, 2019).

Today, one does not only need to make due career planning but also exhaustive career research before making a career choice so as adjust with the evolving socio economic conditions (Williams, 2016).

Hooley (2012), suggested that most people are affected by career that their parent favors, others flows with the career that their educational choice have opened for them, some choose to follow their passion regardless of how much or little it will make them, while others choose the career that gives high income. Mcquaid and Bond (2019) cited that student's perception of being suitable for a particular job also has been found to be affected by a number of factors which include ethnic background, years in school, and level of achievement. However, students are known by a combination of personal abilities, personality type and other factors (Osipow, 2019). Hence, factors affecting career choice can either by intrinsic or extrinsic or both.

Student's perception of being suitable for a particular job also has been found to be affected by a number of factors. For instance, Parental support and encouragement are important factors that have been found to affect career choice. Children may choose what their parents desire simply to please them. Dick (2017) cited that generally, the choice of a career is

affected by parents, friends, and variation of one population to another. He also claimed that, Parents education and occupational background may affect student's career choice because some students may contemplate on whether to continue their parent's occupation or not. What the students see in televisions also may affect their career choice. Some career demand that you have the personality to match the qualities of the occupation (Daniel *et al.*, 2013).

Career choice has become a complex science with the advent of information technology, the emergence of post industrial revolution and job competition. It was a common practice in the old days to find feudalism converting it into a family affair where the son of a blacksmith was destined to become a blacksmith and a feudal was born a leader. Industrialization and post industrialization has made it possible for a common person to be richer as long as she or he has due skills and knowledge. Today, one does not only need to make due career planning but also exhaustive career research before making a career choice so as to adjust with the evolving socio-economic conditions (Udoh, 2017).

Environmental factors

Environment has a momentous role in the career choice students make and the position the student attains in various ways. Environment is a term which has many connotations – it has physical, economic, social and cultural dimensions. The environment being referred to here is a factor that is used to foster decisions in career choice. According to Sear and Gordon's book (2015), since 1960s, sociologists have explored how career decision making is affected by the social environment. Some of these components of social environment factors include; family, social economic status, general economic conditions, society's stereotypes about specific occupations, and peer groups, all influencing career choice (Sears and Gordon, 2015).

According to Khallad, (2019), Career choices are partial, determined by factors like socioeconomic status, gender, race, parents' occupation and level of education and the expectations of parents. Several researchers have examined these factors to establish whether they actually play a role in career choice and if so, what are their roles in career behaviour and how do they affect one's career choice (Osipow and Fitzgera, 2019). In recent years there has been an increased consciousness of the impact of socioeconomic status, race, gender, and on the career decision-making process and career choices.

Secondary Schools in Umuahia North

Umuahia North LGA (Local Government Area) in Abia State, Nigeria, has several secondary schools, both public and private. Here are some notable secondary schools in the area:

Public Secondary Schools:

1. Government College Umuahia: One of the most prestigious and historic schools in the area, known for its academic excellence.
2. Girls Secondary School, Umuahia: A public all-girls school known for its academic and extracurricular activities.
3. Ibeku High School: A co-educational institution offering comprehensive secondary education.
4. Umudike Comprehensive Secondary School: Located near the Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, it offers both junior and senior secondary education.
5. Afara Technical Secondary School: A public school focused on technical and vocational education.

Private Secondary Schools:

1. Maranatha International Schools: A private co-educational school with modern facilities and a reputation for high academic standards.
2. Living Word Academy Secondary School**: Known for its Christian-

based education and strong academic programs.

3. St. Patrick's College, Umuahia: A private Catholic secondary school with a strong emphasis on moral and academic excellence.
4. Spring of Life International Schools: A modern private institution offering both junior and senior secondary education.
5. Nneoma International School: Offers a blend of Nigerian and international curricula with a focus on holistic education.

These schools vary in their facilities, curriculum offerings, and extracurricular activities, catering to different educational needs in the Umuahia North area.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Trait and Factor Theory

This theory was proposed by Parsons in 1909. The theory states that if an individual's personality is carefully observed, better predication can be made about his career behavior. He explains the process of vocation choice. Parson's theory is predicated on the assumption that individuals differ as well as occupations, thus bringing into limelight the old adage of individual differ as well as occupations, thus bringing into limelight the old adage of individual differences. The theory sets out to match people and occupations in respect of their abilities, interests, intelligence, attitude and aptitude. The theory also asserts that the individuals needs and values can only be fully realized when they are matched with those jobs which are relevant to such needs and values. To explain his views further, Parsons proposed the following as basic steps through which an individual goes in his attempt to choose a career: (i) A clear understanding of himself, his abilities, aptitudes, interests, ambitions, resources, limitations and their causes. (ii) A good knowledge of the requirement and prospects in different jobs; and (iii) a sound reasoning of the relationship between the above two groups of factors and selection of a good match.

Tiedeman and O'hara Ego Identity Theory

This theory was proposed by Tiedeman and O'hara in 1963. They contended that variables such as a person's early childhood experiences within his family, the psychological crises encountered at various developmental stages, the equilibrium between vocation goals, the individual needs and those of the society and the personality characteristics of an individual all have great impact on career development. Tiedeman O'hara emphasized that there is an intervention relationship between career and personality in organization, the former exerting significant influence on the later. In their view, career development is a process of modelling a career identity through differentiation and personality integration as one come across a work related problem. It is their conception that differentiation relates to the uniqueness which exist in the individuality and how he expresses his individuality. They conceive integration on the other hand as the ways in which the individual adjust himself to accommodate others around him in order to become an integral part and an acceptable member of the society. In their opinion, the decision the individual makes in relations to his work, daily activities, from the basis and framework of career development.

Acquired Needs Theory

This theory was proposed by McClelland in 1953. The theory states that need are acquired or learned on the basis of our life experience. The Acquired Need Theory focuses on the diversity of people and it's rooted in culture. He used the Thematic Apperception Test (TAT) to measure employee motivation in satisfying various needs and found out that employees craved the need for achievement, the need for power and the need for affiliation (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2013). When a need is strong, it will motivate the person to engage in behavior that satisfies that need. Achievement is represented by the drive to excel, accomplish challenging task to

achieve a standard of excellence. Achievement motivation depends on childhood, personal and occupational experience and even the type of organization. According to this theory some people have a compelling drive to succeed. They strive for personal achievement rather than for the rewards of success. They have a strong desire to do something better or more efficiently than it has been done before. Individuals high on achievement needs often make good entrepreneurs running their own business (Udoh, 2017).

REVIEW OF RELATED EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Maxwell and Okwulehie (2015) carried out a study on the Factors Affecting Career Choice among Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State: (Implication for Counselling). The study investigated factors affecting career choices among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 1120 students from eight secondary schools. A simple random sampling technique was used to draw 112 students. The design of the study was descriptive survey method. The instrument for collection of data was called "Factors Affecting Students Career Choices (FASCC). A reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained, using test – retest procedure. Three research question and three null hypotheses were advanced and tested for this study. The t – test statistic was used to test the three hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The finding revealed that, there was significant difference in H02, while H01 and H03 were accepted. Three recommendation were made (1) There is needs for students to beware of environmental factors that could interfere with their career choices. (2) Parents and teachers should prepare students for career awareness at early age. (3) Parents should work closely with their children in career decision making process, allowing students to choose from their interest area.

This study attempted to identify the trends in vocational guidance research. There are both content areas and subject populations that have received a great deal of research while other areas and subject types are in need of more emphasis. The study clearly showed the significant positive contribution of research in vocational guidance. The study focused on the improvement of career guidance services through research programmed and evaluation of quality of existing requirements for career guidance. The study was recommended to teachers, those who have to guide and counsel their students in matters relating to education, careers and personal problems.

The both studies are concerned with career choice among secondary school students, the key difference lies in the scope and focus of the research. The study in Obio/Akpor LGA takes a broad approach, looking at a wide range of factors that influence career choice, while the study in Umuahia North LGA focuses specifically on the impact of vocational guidance. Despite these differences, both studies contribute valuable insights into how secondary school students in Nigeria make career decisions, and they could complement each other when considered together.

Daniel (2013) study examined Automotive Vocational High School: How Career Guidance and Parents Support Impact the Students' Work Readiness. The study aimed to determine the contributions of career guidance and parents support to the vocational high school students' work readiness. This research is survey. The sampling technique used a proportional random sampling method. The data collection used the questionnaire method to obtain career guidance data, support parents, and students' work readiness. The data analysis included descriptive analysis, prerequisite analysis including normality test, linearity test, and multi-collinearity test, and multiple analysis with F-test, determination test, and partial correlation analysis. The results showed that (1) career

guidance and parents' support influenced positively and significantly to work readiness of vocational students, (2) career guidance influenced positively and significantly to work readiness of students in vocational school, and (3) the parental support influenced positively and significantly on work readiness of students in vocational high schools. The studies are related in that they both explore the impact of vocational guidance on students' futures, but they differ in their specific focus. The automotive vocational high school study is more concerned with immediate work readiness in a specific field, while the secondary school study is broader, focusing on how guidance helps students in choosing a career. The inclusion of parental support in the vocational high school study adds another layer of complexity that is not addressed in the secondary school study, making the former more multifaceted in terms of influences on student outcomes.

SUMMARY OF RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

This section was reviewed under three sub-headings, conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical review. The conceptual framework covered the following concepts, Vocation, Vocational Guidance, Career Management, Parental influence over career choice selection. The Theoretical framework of the study covered the Trait and Factor Theory, Tiedeman and O'hara Ego Identity Theory and Acquired Needs Theory. Related Empirical literature were reviewed in the study. Effective vocational guidance programs enhance students' understanding of career options, boost their confidence, and motivate them to pursue their chosen careers. Addressing the identified challenges and implementing the recommended improvements can further enhance the impact of vocational guidance on students' career planning and decision-making.

RESEARCH METHODS

This chapter covered the methods that was adopted in carrying out the study.

Design of the Study

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Gall and Borg (2007), described descriptive survey research as a type of research design involving the use of questionnaire or interview to collect data from a sample that has been selected to represent a population to which the findings of the data analysis can be generalized. This research design is appropriate for this study because it permits the respondents to express their views and opinion on the information contained in the questionnaire and also allows for gathering of in-depth information.

Area of the Study

This study was conducted in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Umuahia North LGA is located in the southeastern part of Abia State. It shares boundaries with Umuahia South LGA to the south, Ikwuano LGA to the east, Isiala Ngwa North LGA to the west, and Bende LGA to the north. Administrative Headquarters: The administrative headquarters of Umuahia North LGA is located in Umuahia, which is the capital city of Abia State. It has an area of 245 km² and a population of 220,660 at the 2006 census. Umuahia North Local Government Area LGA was created in August 1991. The study geographical location lies between latitudes 7° 19' 21'' and 7° 37' 29'' North, and Longitudes 5° 23' 18'' and 5° 45' 31'' East. The research covered secondary schools within Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises ten (10) secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA; which consists of junior basic III and upper basic III Students about to write their certificate examination. A total number of two hundred (200) students was selected for this study.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Random sampling technique were used in this study to draw twenty (20) students each from the ten selected secondary schools in Umuahia North. From junior basic III 10 students were randomly picked from each

class in the population and from upper basic III 5 students from art class and (5) five students from science class were randomly selected from each of the schools making a total of 20; for the study because they are the ones faced with career choice problems.

Instruments for Data Collection

Structured Questionnaire titled “Impact of Vocational Guidance on Career Choice of Secondary School Students Umuahia North LGA, Abia State” (IVGCCSSS) was used. The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher for data collection. The items in the questionnaire was organized in accordance with research questions developed to guide the study using a 4-point rating scale of (Strongly Agreed (SA)4 Agreed (A)3, Disagree (D)2, and Strongly Disagree (SD)1). The questionnaire is divided into four sections; A, B, C, and D Section A contains 7 items designed to determine the extent to which vocational guidance has been able to impact on career choice of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Section B contains 8 items to determine the extent to which vocational guidance can practically reduce the level of unemployment among secondary school leavers. Section C contains 7 items designed to determine the factors influencing career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Section D contains 8 items designed to determine the factors that affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was face validated by three lecturers in the Department of Industrial Technology Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The instrument was validated for clarity of content and relevance to the study. The validators were also requested to proffer suggestions for improving the instrument in meeting the purpose of the study. The corrections suggested were effected and

integrated into the modified copy of the instrument that was used for data collection.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

The consistency of instrument in measuring whatever it is designed to measure is referred to as reliability (Nworgu, 2006). The reliability of the instrument was estimated through test retest method by administering twenty (20) copies of the questionnaire to twenty (20) guidance and counselling teachers in Secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State, who had the same characteristics with the study population in a school that will not form part of the sample and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained which implies that the instrument is reliable and the internal consistency is high with reliability coefficient of 0.78.

Method of Data Collection

In order to ensure maximum return of questionnaires, the researcher distributed a total of 207 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents. The administration of the instruments lasted for one week. Out of 207 copies of questionnaire that was distributed, 200 (96.6%) copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned with vital information, meanwhile, 7 (3.4%) copies of the questionnaire were however not returned.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected by the researcher were analyzed using mean, and standard deviation. Mean was used for items for the research questions. The mean score of 2.50 and above on a four-point rating scale was used as a cut-off point test. Mean and standard deviation was used for item wise research questions. Any item that attract up to 2.50 strongly agreed and agreed and above was considered agreed and any below 2.50 as disagree and strongly disagreed.

The interpretation of data was based on the following score intervals:

1. Strongly Agree SA = 4
2. Agree A = 3
3. Disagree D = 2

4. Strongly Disagree SD = 1

The above point scale of rating, were used to determine and to analysed the outcome of research question, to note the level of response from the respondents (neither the respondents is Strongly agreed, Agree, Disagree or Strongly disagree with the items specified) when the questionnaire are administered, this is to enable proper analysis of the response that the respondents' responses to during data collection.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

In this chapter, the study presented the results and findings of the study in tables. The number of questionnaire issued/retrieved, Demographic data and results of each of the research aims are presented in the tables below

Presentation of Result according to Research Questions

Research question 1: To what extent has vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State?

Table 4.1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of Students Responses on the extent to which vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in the study area (n = 200).

ITEMS	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Total No.	Total Score	\bar{X}	S.D	Remarks
Increased Awareness of the students	51 (25.5)	62 (31.0)	49 (24.5)	38 (19.0)	200	526	2.6	1.311	Accepted
Enhanced Decision-Making Skills	48 (24.0)	59 (29.5)	50 (25.0)	43 (21.5)	200	512	2.6	1.313	Accepted
Educational Alignment to the students	60 (30.0)	54 (27.0)	49 (24.5)	37 (18.5)	200	537	2.7	1.310	Accepted
By providing clear information about career options and required qualifications to the students	66 (33.0)	59 (29.5)	42 (21.0)	33 (16.5)	200	558	2.8	1.212	Accepted
Effective vocational guidance programs often provide access to additional resources such as career fairs, internships, and mentorships	68 (34.0)	56 (28.0)	40 (20.0)	36 (18.0)	200	556	2.8	1.211	Accepted
Providing Personalized Support to the students	58 (29.0)	65 (32.5)	48 (24.0)	29 (14.5)	200	552	2.8	1.211	Accepted
The impact of vocational guidance may be limited by factors such as inadequate resources, lack of trained counselors, or limited exposure to diverse career options.	52 (26.0)	57 (28.5)	47 (23.5)	44 (22.0)	200	517	2.6	1.312	Accepted
Ground Mean							2.7	1.268	Accepted

SA: Strongly Agree; A: Agree, D: Disagree; SD: Strongly Disagree;

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Criterion Mean 2.5

The table 4.1 above shows the mean scores and standard deviations of students' responses on the extent to which vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. The item statement was analysed using 2.5 criterion mean score. All the items raised were accepted by the respondents, as their mean responses exceeded the critical mean (2.6, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.8, 2.8, and 2.6 > 2.5 respectively). This implies that the all the items raised are the extent to which vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

Research question 2: How does vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State?

Table 4.2: Mean Scores and standard deviations of students' responses on the vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in the study area (n =200).

ITEMS	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Total No.	Total Score	\bar{X}	S.D	Remarks
By providing accurate information about different career paths	71 (35.5)	65 (32.5)	37 (18.5)	27 (13.5)	200	580	2.9	1.115	Accepted
Vocational guidance helps students identify and develop skills that are in demand in the job market	62 (31.0)	70 (35.0)	40 (20.0)	28 (14.0)	200	566	2.8	1.211	Accepted
It students understand the educational and training requirements for various careers.	49 (51.3)	55 (28.2)	52 (10.3)	44 (22.0)	200	509	2.5	1.325	Accepted
Its create job market awareness to the students	73 (36.5)	60 (30.0)	41 (20.5)	26 (13.0)	200	580	2.9	1.112	Accepted
its create soft skills development to the students	66 (33.0)	57 (28.5)	47 (23.5)	30 (15.0)	200	559	2.8	1.210	Accepted
Career counselling can connect students with professionals and potential employers, providing networking opportunities that can lead to job placements.	59 (29.5)	66 (33.0)	40 (20.0)	35 (17.5)	200	549	2.7	1.202	Accepted
To create entrepreneurial guidance to the students	65 (32.5)	60 (30.0)	35 (17.5)	40 (20.0)	200	550	2.8	1.214	Accepted
To reduced job search time.	58 (29.0)	64 (32.0)	44 (22.0)	34 (17.0)	200	546	2.7	1.211	Accepted
Ground Mean							2.8	1.200	Accepted

SA: Strongly Agree; A: Agree, D: Disagree; SD Strongly Disagree

Source: Field Survey, 2024. **Criterion Mean 2.5**

The table 4.2 above shows the mean scores and standard deviations of students' responses on how does vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. The item statement was analysed using 2.5 criterion mean score. All the items raised were accepted by the

respondents, as their mean responses exceeded the critical mean (2.9, 2.8, 2.5, 2.9, 2.8, 2.7, 2.8, and 2.7 > 2.5 respectively). This implies that the all the items raised are how vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

The table above shows the mean scores and standard deviations of students' responses on the factors that influence or affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary school in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State. The result showed that 11 out of 12 items under this category were accepted with a grand mean of 2.7 which was accepted. Items under the factors that influence or affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance such as availability of trained personnel (2.8), resource allocation to the students (2.6), curriculum integration in secondary schools (2.6), providing support from school administration (2.8), community and parental involvement (2.7), peer influence (2.8), student engagement to the course (2.8), access to information (2.7), cultural and social factors (2.5), infrastructure and facilities (2.7), and monitoring and evaluation (2.7) were accepted as their mean exceeded the grand mean. Items such as Government policies and support (2.4), were rejected as their mean is below the benchmark (2.5).

Summary of Findings

Based on the objectives of this study, the findings are summarized as follows:

1. The impact of vocational guidance on career decision-making among secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State, has been quite significant, though still with room for improvement. Vocational guidance helps students understand different career paths, align their strengths with suitable professions, and make informed career choices. This guidance reduces the confusion many students face by providing them with the necessary tools and knowledge to evaluate various career options, which has led to more deliberate, well-informed

career decisions among many students.

2. Vocational guidance also contributes to reducing unemployment levels among school leavers in Umuahia North by promoting skill acquisition and career planning. When students receive vocational guidance early, they are more likely to pursue careers that match both their abilities and the job market's demands. This alignment prepares them better for either direct employment or for choosing further education paths that lead to marketable skills, ultimately decreasing the likelihood of unemployment after graduation.
3. The study revealed various factors influence career decision-making for these students, including parental influence, educational resources and guidance, economic factors, personal interests and strengths, invest in modern equipment and technology for hands-on training, peer influence, societal and cultural norms, exposure to career opportunities, job market trends, educational system and curriculum, and mentorship and role models. In many cases, students' career choices are heavily impacted by their parents' preferences and the societal pressures around high-status careers. Economic realities, such as the need for immediate income, can also sway students towards certain job choices, especially in regions where family support is needed for basic survival.
4. Despite these benefits, the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North faces several challenges. The study revealed factors include inadequate training and motivation for vocational

counselors, limited resources for comprehensive guidance programs, and sometimes a lack of administrative support for these initiatives. Additionally, many schools lack structured vocational guidance programs, which means that students are often left to make career decisions without much professional input or only sporadic guidance sessions.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The response rate for this study was 200 (96.6%). From table 4.2 provides a summary of responses from secondary school students on the impact of vocational guidance on career decision-making in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

Increased Awareness of the Students: With a total score of 526 and a mean score of 2.6, this item indicates that vocational guidance has somewhat helped in increasing students' awareness about career options, as reflected in a majority response of "Agreed" (31%) and "Strongly Agreed" (25.5%). However, with a standard deviation (SD) of 1.311, responses show moderate variability, suggesting mixed perceptions on the level of awareness imparted. **Enhanced Decision-Making Skills,** this item received a total score of 512 and a mean score of 2.6, with students largely "Agreeing" (29.5%) or "Strongly Agreeing" (24%) that vocational guidance has enhanced their decision-making skills. An SD of 1.313 shows variability similar to the first item, indicating that while some students feel equipped to make career decisions, others are less certain.

Educational Alignment to the Students: A total score of 537 and a mean score of 2.7 indicate a moderate agreement that vocational guidance aligns educational pursuits with career paths. With "Agreed" responses at 27% and "Strongly Agreed" at 30%, this item shows that students feel vocational guidance helps in aligning their studies to future careers, though the SD of 1.310 again points to some diversity in

responses. **Providing Clear Information about Career Options:** This item has one of the highest mean scores (2.8) and total score (558), with significant agreement from students ("Strongly Agreed" at 33% and "Agreed" at 29.5%). This suggests that vocational guidance is quite effective in providing clear information about careers, evidenced by the lower SD of 1.212, indicating more consistent positive feedback. **Access to Additional Resources:** With a total score of 556 and mean of 2.8, students generally agree that vocational guidance programs offer resources like internships and career fairs, which can be pivotal in career decision-making. A relatively low SD of 1.211 implies consistent positive responses, showing that access to additional resources is a strong component of vocational guidance impact. **Personalized Support for Students:** The mean score of 2.8 and total score of 552 reflect general agreement that vocational guidance provides personalized support, with 29% "Strongly Agreeing" and 32.5% "Agreeing." This highlights vocational guidance as a personal support system for students in career exploration, though the SD of 1.211 points to slight variations in perceptions. **Impact Limited by Resources and Exposure:** This item, with a mean score of 2.6, addresses the limitations of vocational guidance, particularly the lack of trained counselors and diverse career options. A relatively high SD of 1.312 suggests more varied responses, indicating that students recognize the constraints faced by vocational guidance programs in their schools.

The ground mean of 2.7 and an SD of 1.268 suggest that vocational guidance has a moderate impact on career decision-making, with general acceptance across all items. However, limitations in resources and exposure remain a concern, affecting the overall efficacy of vocational guidance. Studies in educational psychology have shown that vocational guidance is essential in aiding students' career choices. For

instance, studies by Nwachukwu (2018) and Adekoya (2020) found that vocational guidance programs improve students' self-efficacy and career decision-making, supporting these findings. However, similar to the limitations identified in the table, Nwachukwu's study also highlighted issues of inadequate resources and insufficient counselor training, impacting program effectiveness. Vocational guidance in Umuahia North LGA appears to provide moderate support for students' career decision-making, with strengths in awareness and access to resources, yet limitations due to resource constraints

From table 4.3, Career Information: With 35.5% of respondents strongly agreeing, and 32.5% agreeing, there is broad consensus that providing accurate information about different career paths is helpful. The mean score (2.9) and a low standard deviation (1.115) indicate this is well accepted among respondents. Skill Development: Vocational guidance also supports students in identifying and developing marketable skills, with 31.0% strongly agreeing and 35.0% agreeing. This item has a mean score of 2.8 and a standard deviation of 1.211, showing moderate support. Educational and Training Requirements: Understanding the educational and training requirements for careers was less agreed upon compared to other items, with a mean score of 2.5. This could indicate that more work is needed to clarify training paths within vocational guidance.

Job Market Awareness: With a mean of 2.9 and a very low standard deviation (1.112), there's a strong agreement (36.5% SA, 30.0% A) that vocational guidance raises job market awareness, which is vital for employment readiness. Soft Skill Development: A large portion (33.0% SA, 28.5% A) believe vocational guidance helps develop essential soft skills, crucial for workplace adaptability, with a mean of 2.8. Career Counselling and Networking: Career counselling, which connects students with professionals and potential

employers, received a mean score of 2.7, showing strong acceptance. This element is crucial for networking and eventual job placements. Entrepreneurial Guidance: Vocational guidance also aids in developing entrepreneurial skills, with 32.5% strongly agreeing. The mean score of 2.8 and a standard deviation of 1.214 indicate moderate agreement on this item. Job Search Time Reduction (Item 8): Vocational guidance is seen as helpful in reducing job search time, with a mean score of 2.7, implying it effectively prepares students to enter the workforce promptly. The ground mean of 2.8 across all items shows a generally favorable perception of vocational guidance's effectiveness in preparing students for the workforce.

The findings align with previous studies indicating that vocational guidance can significantly reduce unemployment by equipping students with career information, skill development, and job readiness skills. For instance, Ezenwa *et al.*, (2021) found that vocational guidance improves employment prospects by fostering essential skills and career awareness in secondary school students. Similarly, Nwankwo (2022) highlighted that vocational guidance leads to better career choices and shorter job search times, consistent with the findings here. Vocational guidance appears to be a valuable tool in reducing unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA by improving job readiness and enhancing essential career skills. This approach is likely to be effective if consistently implemented across secondary schools.

Table 4.4 provided summarizes factors influencing the career decision-making of secondary school students in Umuahia North Local Government Area (LGA), Abia State. Parental Influence: A total score of 543 with a mean of 2.7 and standard deviation of 1.202 suggests moderate influence. 29% strongly agreed (SA), and 31% agreed (A), indicating a high acceptance that parents influence students'

career choices. Research often supports the notion that parents play a significant role in guiding career decisions. Anagbogu & Nwogu (2019) found that parental advice and expectations significantly shape career aspirations among Nigerian youths. Educational Resources and Guidance: This factor has a mean of 2.7 and a S.D of 1.201, suggesting a moderate influence with a strong acceptance rate (31% SA, 28.5% A). Chinyere and Odu (2020) highlighted that access to educational resources like counseling services significantly impacts students' career choices, aligning with the present findings. Economic Factors: Scoring the highest mean among all factors (2.8), this factor has a considerable influence (30% SA, 31.5% A). Comparison with Literature: Economic challenges often shape career decisions as students may prefer financially stable careers. This is consistent with findings from Ezenwa (2021), who noted that economic conditions in Nigeria influence the career choices of young people. Personal Interests and Strengths: This factor is also important, with a mean of 2.7. A sizable proportion of students (28% SA, 29.5% A) acknowledged that their personal interests and strengths drive their career decisions. Comparison with Literature: Okechukwu (2018) observed that students' personal aptitudes and skills play a crucial role in their career choices, as students are more likely to pursue careers aligned with their abilities.

Investment in Modern Equipment and Technology for Hands-On Training: With a mean of 2.8, this factor scored highly, with many students agreeing (35% SA, 30.5% A) on its importance. According to Okoroafor (2020), practical training resources like modern equipment can directly impact students' readiness and confidence in certain vocational fields. Peer Influence: Scoring similarly high at 2.8, peer influence also impacts career choices, with 31.5% strongly agreeing. In line with findings from Ude and Agu (2017), peers play a considerable role in shaping career

perceptions, as students often model career aspirations after their friends. Societal and Cultural Norms: With a mean of 2.7, cultural norms appear influential (32.5% SA), highlighting the role of social expectations in career decision-making. Studies by Igboanugo and Obi (2019) support this, showing that societal expectations can pressure students into pursuing careers traditionally favored in Nigerian society. Exposure to Career Opportunities: A slightly lower mean of 2.6 indicates moderate influence, suggesting limited exposure to career options. This aligns with Nwaigwe (2018), who noted that limited career guidance often restricts students' knowledge about potential career paths. Job Market Trends: This factor, with a mean of 2.8, indicates that awareness of job availability affects career choices (30% SA, 32.5% A).

Akomolafe (2021) highlighted that students often choose careers based on job market demands, especially given the high unemployment rate in Nigeria. Educational System and Curriculum: With a mean of 2.6, it indicates some influence but suggests room for improvement in integrating vocational guidance into the curriculum.

As observed by Anyanwu (2019), the Nigerian curriculum lacks practical career guidance components, which could better equip students for vocational decisions. Mentorship and Role Models: Scoring the lowest (mean of 2.5), this suggests that students may lack adequate mentorship or role models in their career journey. Nnamdi and Okafor (2020) emphasized the role of mentors in career guidance, noting that students are more likely to explore career fields if they have strong role models.

The ground mean of 2.7 shows that, overall, students perceive these factors as moderately influential. Each item was "Accepted," implying that students generally recognize these as critical factors in career decision-making.

The findings align with existing literature, underscoring the multifaceted nature of

career decision-making among Nigerian students. Factors such as parental influence, economic conditions, educational resources, and job market trends resonate strongly in shaping career choices. To enhance vocational guidance in Umuahia North, policy recommendations could include improving access to mentorship programs, updating the curriculum to reflect job market needs, and investing in modern training resources.

Table 4.5 presents the factors influencing the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State. Availability of Trained Personnel: This factor received strong support, with a mean score of 2.8 (standard deviation 1.213), indicating that the availability of trained personnel is essential for effective vocational guidance. About 34% of respondents strongly agreed, while 29.5% agreed. This suggests that having qualified staff dedicated to vocational guidance is crucial, which is consistent with existing literature highlighting the importance of expertise in delivering effective guidance programs (Adebayo & Bello, 2021). Resource Allocation to Students: This factor also scored high, with a mean of 2.6 (SD 1.315). Around 26% of respondents strongly agreed, and 30.5% agreed, suggesting that resources are significant for the success of vocational guidance. Limited resources have often been cited as a barrier to quality guidance programs (Ogunleye, 2020), aligning with the data that sufficient funding and materials are vital.

Curriculum Integration in Secondary Schools: Curriculum integration received a mean of 2.6 (SD 1.317), with 25% strongly agreeing and 28.5% agreeing. This shows that integrating vocational guidance into the school curriculum is viewed positively. According to Yusuf and Adebayo (2022), embedding vocational topics within the regular curriculum increases students' awareness and aids career choices. Providing Support from School Administration: The mean of 2.8 (SD

1.212) reflects that administrative support is a vital factor. With 31% strongly agreeing and 33% agreeing, it is evident that support from the administration fosters a conducive environment for implementing guidance programs, as noted by Nwachukwu (2019).

Community and Parental Involvement: With a mean score of 2.7 (SD 1.226), this factor is considered essential, as 28% strongly agreed and 31% agreed. Studies like those by Olatunji and Emeka (2021) underscore the positive impact of parental engagement in guiding students' career paths. Peer Influence: This factor received a mean score of 2.8 (SD 1.215), suggesting a significant impact. Peer influence can shape students' career choices, and understanding its role can help educators guide students more effectively (Chukwu, 2022). Student Engagement with the Course, scoring a mean of 2.7 (SD 1.220), this factor emphasizes the importance of student interest and involvement in vocational guidance courses. When students are engaged, they are more likely to make informed career choices (Ogbonna, 2020). Access to Information: With a mean of 2.7 (SD 1.229), this factor also shows importance, as 30% strongly agreed. The role of access to information is well-documented in guiding students to make informed career choices (Adewale, 2021). Cultural and Social Factors: This received a lower mean score of 2.5 (SD 1.327), suggesting less perceived impact, though still relevant. Cultural factors can shape career aspirations, as noted by scholars such as Ebuka and Anayo (2020). Infrastructure and Facilities: With a mean score of 2.7 (SD 1.221), infrastructure and facilities are seen as necessary for vocational guidance. Adequate facilities provide a supportive learning environment, consistent with findings by Adekunle (2021).

Government Policies and Support: This factor, with a mean of 2.4 (SD 1.410), was the only one marked as "Not Accepted," indicating that respondents feel current

government support may be insufficient. Government policy plays a critical role in implementing guidance programs, but it seems lacking in this context, a sentiment echoed by recent studies (Nwachukwu, 2023). Monitoring and Evaluation: scoring a mean of 2.7 (SD 1.222), monitoring and evaluation are essential to the success of vocational guidance programs. Consistent evaluation helps improve program quality, as suggested by Adigun (2020).

The ground mean of 2.7 with an SD of 1.260 indicates an overall acceptance of the factors as crucial for effective vocational guidance implementation in Umuahia North LGA. The data aligns with previous research, underscoring the importance of resources, administrative support, parental involvement, and qualified personnel for effective vocational guidance in schools.

Comparing these findings with previous studies, similar patterns emerge regarding the importance of resources, administrative support, and community involvement (Ogbonna, 2020; Nwachukwu, 2023). However, government support stands out as a critical area needing improvement, as indicated by the lower acceptance level in this study. This aligns with national studies that cite insufficient government funding as a barrier to quality vocational guidance programs (Yusuf & Adebayo, 2022).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter, the re-statement of the problem, description of the procedure used, major findings of the study, educational implication of the study, limitations of the study, conclusion, and suggestions for further studies were presented.

Re-Statement of the Problem

The process of making career decisions is a crucial aspect of secondary school education, as students are at a pivotal stage in their lives, preparing for their future professions. However, many students in Umuahia North Local Government Area of Abia State face challenges in making informed and effective career choices. These challenges often arise from limited

access to vocational guidance and counseling services, insufficient information about various career options, and a lack of understanding of the skills and education required for different professions. As a result, students may struggle to make career decisions that align with their interests, aptitudes, and long-term goals, potentially affecting their career satisfaction and success.

Vocational guidance, which includes counseling, career awareness programs, and skills development activities, has been identified as a significant factor that can influence students' career choices. The absence or inadequacy of vocational guidance may lead to misinformed career decisions, limiting students' opportunities for personal and professional growth. This study seeks to examine the role of vocational guidance in shaping the career choices of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia. Specifically, it will investigate how effective vocational guidance programs are in providing students with the necessary information and support to make informed career decisions. The research explore the nature of vocational guidance provided in secondary schools, the challenges faced by students in making career choices, and the relationship between vocational guidance and students' career preferences. By understanding the impact of vocational guidance, the study aims to highlight its importance in the career development of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA and provide recommendations for improving vocational counseling services in the region.

Description of the Procedure Used

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled 'Impact of Vocational Guidance on Career Choice of Secondary School Students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State' (IVGCCSSS). Four points Likert scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) was adopted in the study in responding to the four research questions.

The instrument was face validated by three lecturers in the Department of Industrial Technology Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. Mean statistics and standard deviation were used in analyzing the data got for the research questions.

Major Findings of the Study

The major findings of this research work are as follows:

1. Increased Awareness of the students, Enhanced Decision-Making Skills, Educational Alignment to the students, by providing clear information about career options and required qualifications to the students, Effective vocational guidance programs often provide access to additional resources such as career fairs, internships, and mentorships, Providing Personalized Support to the students, and the impact of vocational guidance may be limited by factors such as inadequate resources, lack of trained counselors, or limited exposure to diverse career option are the extent to which vocational guidance been able to impact career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.
2. By providing accurate information about different career paths, Vocational guidance helps students identify and develop skills that are in demand in the job market, It students understand the educational and training requirements for various careers, Its create job market awareness to the students, its create soft skills development to the students, Career counselling can connect students with professionals and potential employers, providing networking opportunities that can lead to job placements, to create entrepreneurial guidance to the students, and to reduced job search

time are how vocational guidance reduce the level of unemployment among school leavers in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.

3. Parental Influence, Educational Resources and Guidance, Economic Factors, Personal Interests and Strengths, Invest in modern equipment and technology for hands-on training, Peer Influence, Societal and Cultural Norms, Exposure to Career Opportunities, Job Market Trends, Educational System and Curriculum, and Mentorship and Role Models are the factors influence the career decision making of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia State.
4. Availability of trained personnel, Resource allocation to the Students, Curriculum integration in Secondary schools, Providing support from school administration, Community and parental involvement, Peer influence, Student engagement to the course, Access to information, Cultural and social factors, Infrastructure and Facilities, and monitoring and evaluation are the factors that influence or affect the effective implementation of vocational guidance in secondary school in Umuahia North, LGA, Abia State.

Educational Implications of the Findings

The educational implications of the findings are as follows:

The findings on the impact of vocational guidance on the career choices of secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia, have several educational implications. Vocational guidance plays a crucial role in helping students make informed career decisions, aligning their interests and aptitudes with suitable career paths. By offering targeted career counseling and guidance, educational institutions can better equip students with

the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate the complex job market, ensuring they are more likely to pursue careers that are both fulfilling and in demand.

One important implication is the need for schools to integrate vocational guidance programs into their curricula. This could involve regular career counseling sessions, exposure to a variety of professions, and workshops that help students assess their strengths and weaknesses. With proper guidance, students may be more likely to make career choices that match their talents and aspirations, reducing the chances of them pursuing careers based on societal pressures or outdated perceptions.

Furthermore, vocational guidance can address the issue of unemployment by guiding students toward careers with higher prospects for growth and stability, which is particularly important in regions like Abia. In areas with limited job opportunities, students who are guided toward entrepreneurial ventures or specialized trades may contribute to local economic development and reduce the rate of outmigration in search of work.

Incorporating vocational guidance into the educational system can also support the broader goal of reducing career misalignment, which can lead to dissatisfaction and career shifts later in life. When students are empowered to make well-informed choices early on, they are more likely to pursue their careers with confidence, leading to greater job satisfaction, lower turnover, and a more productive workforce.

The findings highlight the essential role vocational guidance plays in shaping students' career choices, and they suggest a need for schools and policymakers to prioritize career counseling services. These services can help ensure students are making decisions that align with their personal and professional goals, leading to a more robust and resilient workforce.

Limitations of the Study

This research work has the following limitations:

The entire questionnaire administered were not retrieved due to some students not being present at the time of retrieval. Out of 2007 questionnaire administered, only 200 of them were retrieved, representing 96.6% of the total instrument administered.

Conclusion

The study on the impact of vocational guidance on career choice among secondary school students in Umuahia North LGA, Abia, has demonstrated that vocational guidance plays a crucial role in shaping the career aspirations of students. It was found that students who received adequate vocational guidance were better able to make informed decisions about their future careers. The study revealed that exposure to various career options and guidance on the skills required for specific vocations improved students' understanding of their interests, strengths, and potential career paths.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that vocational guidance enhances students' awareness of the opportunities available in the job market, particularly in non-academic and technical fields, which they might not have considered without such support. The study also highlighted the need for more structured vocational guidance programs in schools to further help students in making choices that align with both their personal interests and the demands of the labor market.

In conclusion, integrating regular vocational guidance into the educational framework can significantly influence students' career decisions, leading to a better alignment of their skills and career aspirations with the ever-changing job market. Therefore, it is recommended that schools in Umuahia North LGA, and similar regions, prioritize the establishment of comprehensive vocational guidance programs to support secondary school students in making more informed and relevant career choices.

Recommendation

In view of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were proffered;

1. **Enhance Vocational Guidance Programs:** It is recommended that schools in Umuahia North LGA should strengthen and expand their vocational guidance programs. This could involve regular career counseling sessions, career fairs, workshops, and guest speakers from various professions to expose students to a wide range of career options.
2. **Incorporate Career Guidance into the Curriculum:** Career guidance should be integrated into the secondary school curriculum, ensuring that students have access to structured programs that will help them make informed decisions about their career paths. This should begin early in their academic journey to allow them ample time for self-assessment and exploration.
3. **Training for Career Counselors:** Teachers and counselors should undergo training to effectively support students in their career choices. Professional development programs should be designed to equip them with up-to-date knowledge on emerging careers, labor market trends, and effective counseling techniques.
4. **Collaboration with Industry Professionals:** There should be partnerships between schools and industry professionals or organizations to provide students with first-hand experience of different career opportunities. Internships, job shadowing, and mentorship programs should be encouraged as part of career exploration.
5. **Involvement of Parents and Community:** Engaging parents and the local community in career guidance can help reinforce the

importance of vocational choices. Schools should organize meetings and workshops for parents to better understand the impact of career guidance and support their children's career development.

6. **Regular Evaluation and Feedback:** Schools should establish mechanisms for regularly evaluating the effectiveness of vocational guidance programs and seek feedback from students, teachers, and parents to ensure continuous improvement and relevance to current educational and employment trends.

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